

WORLD EXPERIENCE AND HISTORICAL ASPECTS OF THE FORMATION OF NGOs IN UZBEKISTAN

*Associate Professor of the Department of Humanities
and Information Technologies, SamSIFL
Bobokulova Khurshida Erkinovna*

Abstract: This article provides a systematic analysis of the evolution of non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs) at the global level, their role in society, and the main stages of their historical development. The study highlights the path taken by Uzbekistan after gaining independence in establishing civil society institutions, examines the legal foundations of the sector, and reveals the dynamics of reforms aimed at modernizing NGO activities. In addition, advanced aspects of international experience are explored, and the specific features of Uzbekistan's national model and its correlation with global standards are substantiated through comparative analysis. The article concludes with scientific and theoretical findings aimed at improving the effectiveness of NGO activities.

Keywords: non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs), civil society, historical evolution, international experience, Uzbekistan model, social partnership, legal reforms, third sector, institutional development.

In the modern world, the establishment of a strong civil society is considered a key criterion of democratic reforms. In this context, non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs), acting as a “golden bridge” between the state and society, have become important actors in addressing social issues. Globally recognized as the “third sector,” these institutions today function as equal partners of state structures in ensuring the protection of human rights, environmental sustainability, and social stability.

Although the history of NGOs dates back to ancient times, their development as an institutional system primarily belongs to the second half of the 20th century. International experience shows that the effectiveness of NGOs largely depends on political will and the legal environment established within a country. Therefore, studying the historical

stages of development in this field in developed countries and adapting their best practices to the national context is of significant scientific relevance.

Therefore, when analyzing this aspect from the perspective of the historical formation of civil society institutions, which constitute the core structural component of non-governmental non-profit organizations, it becomes evident that their development models have been shaped in different regions in accordance with specific socio-economic needs. As emphasized by researchers, civil society is not merely an ideological or doctrinal phenomenon, but also a practical expression of individual freedom and the independent regulation of social relations. On the one hand, this system enables individuals to freely choose their interests; on the other hand, it provides a foundation for approaching social processes from the standpoint of an “independent and active individual. In particular, the formation of these institutions has exhibited distinctive characteristics across different geographical and political contexts:

In the United States, the earliest forms of civil society primarily emerged at the local level—as religious associations, educational institutions, and community-based groups ensuring security within residential areas.

In Western Europe, this process was predominantly economic in nature and developed in the form of independent corporate associations shaped by market economy relations.

In the experience of Germany, the elements of civil society are clearly visible in the example of medieval “guilds.” Such self-governing systems of craftsmen and merchants not only protected professional interests, but also exerted a significant influence on the governance of cities. The formation of European cities such as Florence and Padua as “guild-cities” (townsmen) was also one of the first institutional manifestations of the third sector independent from state administration.¹

This historical experience shows that the formation of civil society institutions is a long evolutionary process. From this point of view, in the history of Uzbekistan, during the years of independence, this process rose to a qualitatively new stage. In particular, as

¹ Ашин Г.К., Кравченко С.А., Лозанский Э.Д. Социология политики. Сравнительный анализ российских и американских политических реалий: Учеб. пособие для высших учебных заведений. - М.: Экзамен, 2001. –С. 608.

a result of the advancement of the principle “From a strong state to a strong civil society”², the system of non-governmental non-profit organizations began to develop consistently.

It should be noted that in the development of civil society institutions, the tradition of a “strong state” is a characteristic feature not only of the East, but also of the political systems of many Western countries. In particular, in such countries as Germany, France, and Japan, the role of the state in ensuring socio-political stability has traditionally been maintained at a high level. The specific feature of this model is that the idea of national unity acquires a priority significance in it, while individual freedom is interpreted in direct connection with state power and institutional stability. That is, a strong state system is considered as the main guarantee of protecting individual interests. In the experience of Germany, non-governmental non-profit organizations and civil society institutions perform the following important functions:

On the path of institutional stability, NGOs have become a strategic partner of the state in solving socio-economic problems and in protecting human rights.

In the function of control, the establishment of systematic public control over the activities of state systems constitutes the foundation of this model. This mechanism serves to increase the responsibility of government bodies before society.

Through the dynamics of mutual cooperation, the development of the non-governmental sector strengthens effective dialogue between the state and society and is considered an important factor in ensuring transparency in governance.³

Thus, this model has formed civil society institutions not as separated from the state, but as a force that develops in harmony with the state, complements it, and exercises control over it.

In international experience, as another distinctive model of regulating the activities of NGOs, the system of the United Kingdom can be cited. In addition to traditional forms of cooperation, there are specialized structures, in particular the Charity Commission, which operates with specific functions. This body, which registers and coordinates

² <https://lex.uz/docs/-2938958>

³ Курбатов В.И. Современная западная социология: Аналитический обзор концепций: Учеб. пособие. – Ростов-на-Дону: Феникс, 2001. – 416с

charitable organizations in England and Wales, ensures that the third sector—considered an integral part of British social life—operates within the framework of the law. The main principle of the activity of this commission consists of ensuring that NGOs pursue socially beneficial goals rather than personal interests, remain independent in governance, and make decisions free from any external illegal influence. The Commission, while assisting in the creation of effective legal, accounting, and management systems for charitable organizations, also continuously monitors economic and legal changes in society. At the same time, as a supervisory body, it has the authority to conduct independent investigations in cases of legal violations, cooperate with the prosecutor's office and the police, and intervene in the activities of organizations in order to preserve their property. A notable feature of the British model is that, although this Commission reports annually to Parliament and the Minister for Social Affairs, it operates, in essence, as an independent body protecting the interests of society as a whole. This, in turn, is considered a high example of ensuring transparency in the activities of NGOs and accountability to society.⁴

The experience of developed Western countries shows that in creating a modern civil society model, priority is given to ensuring the effective participation of non-governmental institutions in public administration. Such an approach, while strengthening the role of civil society institutions in society and governance, also elevates the system of social partnership to a new stage. At the same time, cooperation between the state and NGOs, based on the principles of openness and transparency, enables a deeper systemic analysis of the processes taking place in the third sector.

In particular, the French model is distinguished by the active involvement of non-governmental organizations in the process of forming government policy. Here, advisory councils under ministries and agencies serve as the main mechanism of cooperation with civil society. A distinctive feature of France is that the methods of monitoring the development of civil society are regularly updated, which creates broad opportunities for analyzing the growing role of public associations in the country's life. In this regard, the activities of the Institute for Security Studies in Europe, as well as other analytical centers

⁴ Qarang: Schmitter Ph. Civil society East and West// Consolidation the Third Wave Democracies: Themes and Perspectives/ Ed. by L.Diamond et al. Baltimore and London: The Johns Hopkins U.P., - 1997. – P.239-262.

of France and the European Union, are especially noteworthy. These centers scientifically study the dynamics of cooperation between civil society institutions and state bodies and develop systemic recommendations. Such an analytical approach contributes to the transformation of the non-governmental sector into an important actor not only in the social sphere but also in the development of the state's strategic decisions.⁵

In the United States, strategic priority is given to improving the forms, principles, and directions of cooperation between state bodies and non-governmental non-profit organizations (NGOs) in addressing pressing issues of the socio-economic development of society. In the experience of this country, mechanisms for public oversight over the activities of state authorities and the implementation of adopted legislative acts are characterized by a high level of development. The improvement of organizational and legal cooperation between the state and civil society serves not only to effectively solve urgent social problems but also to increase the socio-economic activity of the population. This, in turn, creates broad opportunities for state bodies in performing important nationwide tasks. In the scientific substantiation of these processes, the role of leading analytical centers and research institutes in the United States is invaluable. In particular, institutions such as the National Democratic Institute (NDI), the Center for Civil Society Studies at Johns Hopkins University, and the International Center for Not-for-Profit Law (ICNL) actively participate in developing the theoretical and practical foundations of cooperation between the state and society.⁶

The analyses show that in the United States, civil society institutions have become one of the main actors not only in the social sphere, but also in political decision-making and in increasing the efficiency of public administration. The integration of parliamentary oversight of state activities with public control further strengthens the principles of openness, transparency, and accountability within the system.

In international experience, advanced principles have developed in close connection with the historical and strategic directions of civil society institution development in

⁵ Чилкот Рональд Х. Теории сравнительной политологии. В поисках парадигмы /Пер. с англ. - М.: ИНФРА-М, Издательство «Весь Мир», 2001.-560 с

⁶ O'Connell Brian. Civil Society: The Underpinnings of American Democracy. Medford, Mass:Tufts University Press, 1999.

Uzbekistan. Concepts characteristic of Western European and United States models, such as openness, social partnership, and public control, have served as a theoretical foundation in establishing the legal framework regulating NGO activities from the earliest years of the country's independence.

In the process of historical development, the positive aspects of institutional structures such as analytical centers in France or specialized commissions in the United Kingdom were studied and incorporated into national legislation as systematic mechanisms ensuring the participation of NGOs in public administration. In particular, as a result of reforms implemented at a new stage of state-building, the institutionalization of public councils under state bodies, as well as the adoption of the "Law on Social Partnership," became an important turning point in elevating the national model to the level of international standards.

Thus, the balance of a "strong state and strong civil society," formed in the international arena, created a unique synthesis in the historical social environment of Uzbekistan. In this process, modern democratic institutions were enriched with the centuries-old institution of the mahalla and Eastern traditions of public participation of our people. As a result, the evolution of NGOs in Uzbekistan has gone beyond the stage of merely providing social services and has reached the level of a socio-political and legal actor that actively participates in defining state strategy and represents the interests of society.

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